

New Trends
in Psychology

Methods of Employee Selection in Nepalese Organizations Based on Internet Technology: A Qualitative Inquiry

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Abstract: Employee selection is the systematic process of choosing the fittest applicant in a vacant position. This qualitative research was conducted to identify the methods and process of employee selection in Nepalese organizations based on internet technology with a convenient sample of 20 spanning a total of 574 minutes of the interview. The data were recorded in virtual audio interviews and analyzed in the framework of content analysis. The methods adopted to select employees in the industry turned out to have seven themes: interview, written examination, assignments, headhunting, referral, and outsourcing. The conclusion is that Nepalese companies adopt some systematic techniques for hiring but they are not scientific enough not to risk loss caused due to wrong hiring decisions.

Keywords: interview; written examination; Nepalese companies; selection procedure; IO Psychology

Introduction

Employee Selection

Employee selection is the systematic process of choosing a suitable applicant for a vacant position in an organization (Adhikari, 2020). It is an important function of the human resource (HR) department. Employee selection is crucially related to the success or failure of an organization because the right hire can contribute to the

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survival and thriving of an organization but a wrong hire can cause various damages to the organization like a disruption in task chain, de-motivation of coworkers, and emotional contagion negatively. Careful selection is important for improved individual and organizational performance and reduces dysfunctional behaviors (Dessler, 2014). A fair and objective selection process is associated with good financial outcomes in organizations (Čanković, 2015).

Employee selection is directly or indirectly related to other human resource (HR) functions like HR planning, job analysis, recruitment, socialization, training and development, performance management, compensation, layoff, and labor relations. Undoubtedly, the HR department should allocate a significant portion of its resources for employee selection. Before that, the management of an organization should prioritize HR management (HRM) as a vital component of management.

Internationally, the following steps are adopted in the employee selection process: first screening interview, application blank, psychological testing, main interview, provisional job offer, background check, medical examination, a permanent job offer (DeCenzo et al., 2013). The order of steps may be altered and some steps may be skipped by some organizations. Some organizations choose to take all candidates through all steps and select required candidates finally. Some organizations take only those candidates to the following step who are deemed best in the preceding steps.

Employee selection is an important HR function that affects various aspects of organizational behavior. For example, in the banking industry, there was seen a positive association between employee selection and employee retention (Khadka, 2013). However, recruitment and selection could not predict retention. Employee turnover is a big concern for the HR department. The less the employer turnover is, the more stable an organization is considered.

Procedure of Selection

Private and public sectors select employees differently. Public sectors are more systematic in recruiting employees even though they may not all be fair. Among the Nepali customers, an organization named the public service commission (PSC) has a good brand as an impartial HR agent of the government. Constitution of Nepal has it that an organization named PSC is given the responsibility to conduct written examination for the vacant positions in civil service, Nepal Army, Nepal Armed Force, Nepal Police, and other federal governmental positions (Public Service

Commission [PSC], 2021). It first announces vacancies through the Gorkhapatra and its webpage. It then takes applications (now online) from candidates. Written examination in one phase or more phases selects out some candidates. Then, there are other selection steps like the interview and practical tests. The process of selection occurs as shown in figure 1. Even though the brand of PSC is associated with impartiality and fairness among people, its recruitment and selection processes are less than perfect. Maharjan & Kim (2016) point out weaknesses like limited inclusiveness, inadequate job descriptions, traditional selection practices, and improper legal, political and managerial methods in recruitment and selection.

In Armed Police Force (APF), employee selection occurs in prescribed format with help of PSC in the phase of written examination (Paudel & Pahari, 2018). The format includes the steps like physical examination, health check-up, practical examination, written examination, and interview. However, the process has not been systematic over the years impacting promotion and thus maintenance of the chain of command.

Many private organizations in Nepal take employees by referral (Adhikari, 2020). Schools and colleges adopt this method mostly. (International) Non-governmental organizations ((I)NGO) also rely on it but some may recruit applicants and take them through processes like written examination and interviews. They formally announce vacancies through mass media, mainly newspapers and online job portals. Generally, senior management positions and technical positions appear to the public as vacant. Some (I)NGOs adopt a policy of transparency. So, all vacancies should come to the mass media.

It seems the HR department's importance has not yet been realized properly in Nepal. For example, in the tea sector, planning, recruitment, selection, and development get a low priority (Rai, 2008) as cited in Pandey, 2011). Other sectors are similar in attitude to HRM. Nevertheless, the growth of industries and the corporate world in Nepal might have altered it. This study will inquire into this issue also as a specific objective.

In the public sector, there is a norm of selecting half of the candidates by open competition and the rest half from the internal promotion (Gautam, 2012). For lower posts, the probation period is six months. For officers and higher posts, it is a year. As mentioned above, PSC is responsible to recommend governmental employees. It now holds written tests for all bodies of the state. It also takes the responsibility of interviews and aptitude tests for civil service. However, other state bodies (including

the public corporations) conduct interviews on their own in the presence of at least one representative of PSC.

Figure 1. Steps of employee selection by public service commission. Adapted from

Source:

<https://dms.nasc.org.np/sites/default/files/documents/recruitment%20and%20selection.pptx>

Methods of Selection

Adhikari (2020) writes in his book ‘Industrial and Organizational (IO) Psychology’, the following tools can be adopted to select employees: psychological tests (like paper-&-pencil, aptitude test, biographical tests, personality tests, intelligence tests, emotional intelligence (EI) tests) and interview. Psychological tests are standard procedures for assessing a sample of behaviors or mental processes. Paper-and-pencil tests are the written tests. Aptitude tests measure candidates’ ability in a particular dimension. Aptitude can be physical or intellectual. Biographical information (or biodata) is the candidates’ information about experiences, qualifications, and skills. Personality tests assess and measure the applicants’ consistent and unique way to act, feel and think. Intelligence tests measure general or specific mental ability. EI tests measure job seekers’ ability to know and manage their own and others’ emotions. Other tests like interest inventories, situational judgment tests, and achievement tests can also be used (Dessler, 2014). Likewise, management assessment centers can also be used.

There are various ways organizations of various nature hire employees. PSC, the constitutional hiring agency which recommends selected candidates for positions of

governmental service, adopts methods like application blanks, written tests, practical tests, interviews, and other suitable methods as shown in figure 1. Affiliates of foreign companies in import practices and values of parent organizations concerning human resource management (Maharjan & Sekiguchi, 2016). Nonetheless, the needs of the local market can compromise them. The three most used sources of recruitment are personal networks, advertisements, and internal promotion (Maharjan & Sekiguchi, 2016). There are not many researches about how private companies have their human capital made.

Use of Technology in Employee Selection

Sending and receiving applications using the internet is already an old phenomenon now. In 2012, the use of computer-based and internet-based testing was very common (Davison et al., 2012). Still, new innovations are being seen in this area. For example, businesses in the hospitality industry are using asynchronous video interviews (AVIs) for employee selection (Torres & Mejia, 2017). In an AVI, the employer first sends questions in text form electronically. The candidates then have to record answers using webcams via some software and send to the employer. The use of social media for human resource (HR) functions is a reality because social media are mainstream now (Landers & Schmidt, 2016). Yet, the use of social media may have chances of errors despite their benefits. Many employers use social media as a source of candidates' information. Adhikari (2020) writes use of a professional network like LinkedIn is okay with a background check. The use of social media sites like Facebook and Twitter for a background check is an intrusion of privacy, and thus unethical. The gamified assessment methods in employee selection may be a new trend (Georgiou et al., 2019). It is the use of games to know candidates' personality, honesty, and abilities among others. Social media like Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn are offering chances for companies to recruit, and opportunities for candidates to find jobs. Companies also can use information about candidates to predict their job performance or withdrawal (Roth et al., 2016).

Employee Selection in Internet-Based Companies

For foreign employment, recruitment agents first advertise in the daily newspaper. Candidates are short-listed based on their application (and relevant documents). The

employers' interview applicants and the fittest ones are selected (Gurung, 2004). The medical examination is the final barrier thus selected candidates have to cross.

There is not much literature on how employees are selected in the organizations that deliver services based on the internet in Nepal. In fact, there is not any literature in the international context also.

Conceptual framework

Basing on the existing literature and personal experience of researchers, the process of selection in Nepal should follow the following pattern:

Figure 2. Conceptual framework for the employee selection process in Nepalese internet-based companies

The most used methods of employee selection tend to be interviews and written examination. Resumes and application letters are most used tools for recruitment.

Objectives of Research

The research aimed to explore the ways, methods, and techniques Nepalese organizations based on internet technology select employees. It also aimed to identify the general pattern of the employee selection process in those companies.

Rationale of Research

The research is expected to contribute to knowledge in IO psychology and human resource management of Nepal. We could not locate previous studies that explored methods of employee selection in Nepalese organizations. So, this research is expected to have an applied part. The relevant companies can get an industry update about how companies similar to them select employees. Similarly, potential future

employees of these companies or job candidates can get ideas about the procedure and get prepared accordingly.

Methods

Design

The research was conducted in a qualitative design. When the design is qualitative, search for rich and thick data is a priority rather than quantification (Braun & Clarke, 2013).

Participants

There were 20 representatives of respective organizations. They were from HR departments (like HR manager/officer), senior management (like CEO), or simply employees. Stoppage of data collection was guided by the concept of theoretical saturation derived from the tradition of grounded theory. This concept lets the researcher “sample and code data until no new categories can be identified” (Willig, 2013). Some characteristics of participating organizations and representatives are given in the following table:

Table 1. Characteristics of Participants

Industry	
<i>Type of organization</i>	<i>Counts</i>
IT Company	9
Financial Institution	4
Media Company	5
HR Agency	1
E-commerce company	1
HR size	
<i>Number of employees</i>	<i>Counts of organizations</i>
Up to 100	11
More than 100	9
Interviewee	
<i>Type of representative interviewed</i>	<i>Counts</i>
Management position	7
HR Pro	2
Employee	11

Procedure

The data were collected by interview method. It was semi-structured. Since the interviews were conducted during the post-lockdown COVID-19 pandemic time, they were taken from the internet using the video streaming tool 'Streamyard' and by direct phone calls. The consent form was read out loud. Permission was taken to audio-record the conversation after oral consent was acquired for the interview. The conversations lasted from 17 to 52 minutes. Because of technical difficulties like the poor audio quality of conversation, and internet disruptions, some conversations took place in two sessions.

Instruments

The semi-structured interview guide was ready in front of the interviewer during interview process. The guide is given in the appendix. The interview was recorded on the laptop connected to the internet. The probing questions were improvised impromptu.

Sampling

Convenient sampling was used. The sample consisted of representatives of organizations based on the internet because of easy accessibility. Data were collected during the pandemic of COVID-19 post-lockdown in Nepal. The sample size was 20 which spanned a total of 574 minutes of the interview. In qualitative research, this size cannot be considered small as most of qualitative research use 12 as basis for theoretical saturation (Roland, 2016). Determination of sample size is contextual and dependent on paradigm chosen. It can be based on judgement and experience (Sandelowski, 1995) also.

Ethics

Ethical guidelines of the American Psychological Association (APA) like informed consent, non-maleficence, confidentiality, privacy, and right to withdraw have been followed. The identity of the research participants or their related organizations has not been shown off anywhere.

Data Analysis

Audio files were first transcribed. The transcribed files were subjected to qualitative content analysis. Data analysis was done manually in the steps of coding and finding themes, and rearranging the themes (reclassification). The technique of note-taking was also used during data analysis.

Results

Even though the companies using internet-technology for service delivery were our population, it is a broad *umbrella* term that includes companies of diverse nature. IT companies were found to select employees by using tasks or assignments. Alternatively, they checked the qualifications of candidates by past portfolios or projects accomplished. For them, educational qualifications did not matter much as long as the candidates could accomplish the tasks they are assigned. Financial organizations had academic qualifications as a must. For example, banks selected Bachelor graduates as trainee assistants and Master graduates as management trainees. News vendors gave authority to chief editors to appoint the news reporters. Job portal (HR agents) used their digital platforms (like webpages) to select employees for themselves. Internet service providers admitted candidates in the lowest position (like phone support employee) and upgrade them to senior positions. There were significant differences in how employees were hired in private and government-owned organizations. In governmental organizations, permanent employees were recommended by the public service commission but temporary or contract workers were appointed by senior management or brought opaquely. These are the unique information about selection methods or criteria. However, there are some commonalities.

The common themes of employee selection methods used by Nepalese companies based on internet companies are given below:

1. Interview

The interview was the most used method for employee selection. In it, the employers tended to know the job candidates' outward personality (like attire, self-presentation), attitude, level of confidence, interests, and knowledge about the company and field/industry. Bankers were expected to show abilities to tolerate or handle stress. Similarly, candidates for banks were supposed to have good communication skills. Some soft skills were desirable in each sector.

We ask behavioral questions. We know many things instantly after we meet candidates; their attire tells us many things about their preparation. We ask 5/6 common questions. Candidates' responses to them tell us a lot about their attitude. And also, about knowledge of job, behaviors, and preparedness.

[P14, HR manager, HR agency/ job portal company]

2. Outsourcing

The growth of online job portals and HR agents had increased the specialization of employee selection in Nepal. The companies based on internet technology also took help from HR agencies to hire the necessary candidates. The outsourcing of employee selection to these HR companies was mainly focused on entry-level positions. Anonymous job posting used to be the norm. Now, online job portals promoted companies to be named in vacancies because they are a great medium for branding. The more the employees were being hired, the stronger the organization was for the clients.

One of three ways is outsourcing vacancies. We give them our requirements and request companies like Merojob and Kumarijob (job portals) to find suitable candidates for us.

[P01, senior management, online specific news portal company]

3. Written examination

The technical aptitude tests (written examination in laypersons' terms) were also conducted. They were mainly paper-and-pencil tests with industry-related and position-related questions. Generally, these written examinations assessed if the candidates were informed about basic concepts and jargon used in the industry or day-to-day operation.

General questions are asked in the written examination. There are tricky questions based on the job description. There may be short-answer-type questions or ready-made questions. Interviews are a follow-up of these questions. I say based on my experience.

[P09, employee, digital wallet company]

4. Headhunting

For higher positions, headhunting was a good option as a selection method. For this, companies took help from HR agencies (and/or online job portals). Headhunting was costlier than the regular selection process but the cost was worth it. Job portals again might be helpful. They had a large database of executives of various organizations and might pinpoint a good fit easily.

Senior-level employees want invisibility in the application. So, it is wise to go from an executive search. We also tell them a salary. We outsource such a search too. It is costlier but the cost is worth it because there is less risk.

[P01, senior management, online specific news portal company]

5. Task accomplishment

Job candidates were given tasks/assignments. If they could accomplish them, they were taken to the next step of the selection process. Tasks were practical problems related to jobs needing a solution. They were mainly technical.

The organization gives tasks to [junior] candidates and identifies their abilities. We know their interests during the interview and the extent of their passion during an internship.

[P20, management, IT company]

6. Referral

Taking the candidates recommended by somebody working already as trusted employees was a good method to select other employees. It is a widely used method all over the world across various industries.

When senior employees are selected, they come from referrals. There is enough background check about them, however. Kathmandu is a small city. All people in the industry may know senior employees working in the industry.

[P15, senior management, IT company]

Based on the responses of participants of the research, the methods of selection can be shown in the series of steps as given below:

Figure 3. The general process of employee selection in internet-based companies. This process is generally applicable for entry-level or mid-level positions but senior-level positions

Even though the common steps are the ones shown in figure 3, some organizations adopt extra steps like group discussion. The order of steps may vary for organizations. All steps also may not be followed. In other words, some steps may be skipped.

In almost all organizations, the selection of employees in junior and senior positions is different. The following table gives a summary of selection methods in these positions:

Table 3. Techniques of selecting employees in senior and junior positions are different

Methods of employee selection	
Junior positions	Senior positions
Outsourcing	Headhunt
Written examination	Interview
Interview	Referral
Technical Aptitude Tests	
Referral	

Low priority for HRM

The companies with few employees were not very knowledgeable about HR issues. They assumed that wrong selection decisions are inevitable. They did not know *everything* about candidates. They had not prioritized HRM much. The tech-companies believed that HRM was also a learning process. It somewhat means that people holding purely technical positions learn on their own as time passes some HR functions. An employee of a news house said that their company adopted an easy strategy of ‘come and go’ cheerfully. Only a few organizations seemed to be clear about HR goals and strategies. They were thinking of making an HR Handbook. Many organizations seemed to be unaware of the importance of HRM. Some employees in news organizations had sensed that the current selection process was inadequate.

Newspapers are displaced by online news portal... Now, the management has almost given up to prevent the turnover of employees. It easily says, “Come cheerfully; go cheerfully”.

[P07, employee, news portal company]

It takes time to know people. When they do not give the desired outcome, we feel as if we hired wrongly. We are thinking of adopting screening means like attitude tests.

[P10, senior management, IT company]

Employee Turnover

All organizations had up to five employees leaving them in a month except one organization in which there was more than 10 turnover per month. This is a rough indication that employees' selection process was not just right. Turnover had lessened during the COVID-19 pandemic because of *employment stagnation in the industry* and the stoppage of employees' flow inter-organizationally. The employee turnover is very low in governmental and semi-governmental organizations as the employees have permanent jobs (and therefore job security) or high prospects of having them shortly.

In banks, the hired employees are more talented than demanded by the positions. When they are not able to utilize the skills they possess, they may be dissatisfied. Moreover, the offices are understaffed. So, the sitting employees are under the pressure of overload. The organizations train a lot but they focus on the weaknesses of employees rather than appreciating positive aspects. There are motivation issues.

COVID-19 pandemic and employee selection

COVID-19 pandemic had lessened employee turnover in most of the organizations. HR managers believed that employee selection had been challenging during that period as they wanted employees to have more integrity since they had to work from home. Some HR professionals missed ordinary days as they believed that virtual interviews were not as delightful as face-to-face interviews.

Some particular businesses had an extra step in the selection process. For example, banks took candidates (of management trainee position) through group discussion to check their leadership ability or ability to be a team player. Candidates might be checked for their capability by giving cases to solve during an interview. Similarly, some organizations might have a physical examination.

Affiliates of international organizations tamed the employee selection process to fit the Nepalese scenario. There were different legal provisions and cultural backgrounds. One such newly established organization organized a fair to both publicize brand and advertise vacancies. Its management members shared the vacancies through their social media individually. They devised a very long application blank to filter candidates who were not passionate.

In governmental organizations, there was haphazardness in hiring contract workers. In news organizations, the executive directors directly and non-transparently appointed them. The employees wished that the selection process was fairer. Specialists could be hired as contract workers in banks rarely. Lest most of the employees came by the formal public process. Generally, executive directors were also politically appointed. The employees wished that they were selected systematically based on merit too. News organizations discriminated against women in selection because news reporters had to work late at night often or go to the field to collect news in off-hours. In banks, few positions did not belong to the management stream. For example, a bank might need an economist who is generally not trained in management stream.

The HR managers suggested an academia-industry tie-up. Similarly, they wished that academia strongly taught students about career planning and skills to hunt for the right jobs properly. In the current situation, many weak job candidates approached the organizations. Some candidates showed *self-obstructing of the unexperienced* error. They wrote in CVs and uttered in interviews the complicated terms they did not know meaning of. When asked what they meant, they were unable to answer and got rejected. They were the barriers created by themselves. HR professionals also suggested fresh graduates be less ambitious about compensation. Some companies provided internship opportunities or entry-level positions to incumbent college-level students. Fresh graduates were offered assistant-level positions.

Some HR professionals showed a bias towards introverts or people with mental problems. They also pointed out that job candidates had the wrong attribution about their personality traits. There was a gap between perception and reality about candidates' personalities.

Discussion

Conclusion

Nepalese companies based on internet technologies generally use methods like an interview, written examination, tasks, interviews to select employees. Since they do not have a highly systematic/scientific procedure of employee selection, they may hire the wrong employees. However, they believe the *probation period* is the solution to this problem.

Some candidates are good at speaking during an interview. Their performance may be subpar, nevertheless. It is the probation period in which they are rightly appraised if they should be continued.

[P14, HR manager, HR agency/job portal company]

Counting on the probation period as a chance to filter the wrong hire may engender some loss to the organization already. The inquiry has got the insight that companies may not ever know that the wrong person was hired. They do not have an adequate performance management mechanism to identify the expected and real performance gap. In this state, a wrongly hired employee may get a chance to exploit the probation period to train themselves to fit in with the organizational needs. The participants have reported a significant employee turnover rate among employees. However, they believe that their hiring practice is enough. Employee turnover might have been affected by factors other than the hiring process also. Nonetheless, it is one. HRM policy consistency (including one for the selection process) was seen to correlate inversely with turnover (Huselid, 1995).

The common process of selection is to go to a written test after recruitment (by shortlisting CVs or application forms). Then companies go for interviews. Some of the companies use tasks/assignments or projects (or portfolios) to take them to a conditional job offer (also called probation period). If candidates pass all these stages successfully, they are given the job *permanently*. The word 'permanently' comes with two scenarios. Some well-established companies may treat selected employees with benefits of provident fund and other facilities. Some flailing and budding companies may nominally use the word. They do not offer any extra 'job security' or commit themselves to ethical and legal binding to give extra care to the employees. Figure 3 above is the model derived after modifying the conceptual framework as the employee selection procedure in Nepalese organizations.

Headhunting is a way to select employees in Nepalese affiliates of foreign companies (Maharjan & Sekiguchi, 2016). This trend has come to local companies also. As Adhikari (2020) points out, the use of psychological testing in an employee is very low in Nepalese organizations based on internet technology according to the present study. Only a company was found to be thinking to use it as a screening tool. However, many companies are using it unknowingly and in an unsystematic manner in different forms like (technical) aptitude tests or written examination (which is a paper-and-pencil test).

The HR professionals' discrimination against introverts and people with mental disorders shows that they are unaware of person-job fit. Unless severely dysfunctional, mental patients are not subpar or harmful. If they can show that they are capable of completing required tasks in a job, they should not be discriminated against on the humanitarian ground.

Attention has not been given to make interviews objective. There might be certain implicit beliefs that bias the decisions made from interviews. Like Highhouse (2008) point out, selectors (like HR professionals) heavily depend on intuition and may carry out biased selection decisions. An example of such bias is the implicit belief that experiences increase the ability to predict human behavior.

The pandemic of COVID-19 caused the stagnation of employee flux from an organization to another. Many companies downsized themselves. A new norm of *working from home* arrived. HR professionals also had a hard time adapting to the *new normal*. Its effect seems to linger in employee selection styles in the future. For example, job seekers may get a chance to do job interviews at home via 'Zoom', 'MS Teams' or 'Google Meet'.

Limitations

The research only used a convenient sample. The sample size was small. As expected, we could not interview all the HR professionals from respective companies. Some of the participants were common employees. So, the findings come from this study can be a source of insight but they should not be the base for generalization. We could have better insight if all the participants were directly related to the management of the personnel. Moreover, the organizations were eclectic in terms of their business and employee size. Findings would have been more useful if we could inquire into homogenous organizations.

Future Researches

This study has focused on broad methods of employee selection. Future researches can explore how the particular methods are used, in greater detail. For example, how are interviews used, what types of interviews are used, what things are being done to reduce cognitive biases that may occur in interviews, etc. can be interesting research questions regarding interviews. Similarly, what kind of questions are being asked in written tests, to what extent are the questions standardized, what kinds of skills are being assessed from candidates in these tests, etc. can be explored regarding

written tests or aptitude tests. This research also overlooks the aspects of recruitment. Future research can focus on how social media are being exploited for recruitment.

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Appendix

Interview guide

1. How do you select employees in your organization?
2. Do you adopt different methods for different positions (senior vs entry-level)? How?
3. Why are you using those particular methods?
4. Have you made some wrong selection decisions? Please elaborate?
5. Do you imagine sometimes that your selection would be better if some things were different? Please clarify?
6. How cooperative is your boss to advance your vision/ability for better HRM?